

Mapping Moving Makers: Mobility in the British Scientific Instrument Trade, 1700-1900

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This paper describes early findings from Tools of Knowledge, a digital humanities project investigating the structure of the Scientific Instrument Trade in Great Britain led by the University of Cambridge in collaboration with the University of Sussex, the National Maritime Museum, and the National Museum of Scotland. The core of the project is based around a legacy database created by Gloria Clifton, Curator Emerita at the National Maritime Museum, which documents the names, addresses, trades, and relations between more than 10,000 British makers and sellers of scientific instruments (and their associates) since 1550. This database is currently in the process of being cleaned, normalised, and modelled semantically against the CIDOC CRM ontology for documenting cultural heritage, and will be augmented with additional data sources including catalogue data from the National Museum of Scotland, the Whipple Museum of the History of Science at Cambridge University and historical records such as the Admiralty Chronometer Ledger held by the National Maritime Museum.

A number of researchers have identified the importance of the spatial context and movement of scientific instrument makers and their institutions to the structure and reception of the trade as a whole (Withers et al., 2008; Schillings and van Wickeren, 2015). Responding to this work, and seeking to build on it by using the combination of precision and scale facilitated by digital methods, our early geospatial investigations have revealed a subset of makers in our database—approximately 500—who moved or established new businesses in more than one town or city. Using a combination of network analysis and GIS work at town, region, and national scales, we have begun to explore the social and spatial structures evident in the data. This initial analysis has suggested a number of spatial patterns which seem significant: the movement of makers from ports such as Liverpool to industrial areas (Manchester, Birmingham); the movement of nautical instrument makers in coastal areas; and the development of the trade in the West Midlands, which is characterised by movement of makers between small- and medium-sized towns.

This paper presents these early results, exploring a number of interrelated questions. Who were these makers, what characterises them, and what can we learn from their similarities and differences, in terms of their identities as individual makers, and in terms of the structure of the trade and its specialisms, at both a regional level and as a whole? What is the overall pattern of the movements of these makers? (From London to the rest of Britain, between England and Scotland, or was business movement a factor of regional trade?) Was it these makers that were key to the growth and spread of the scientific instrument trade? Or were other factors, for example apprenticeship networks, the availability of trade literature, or institutions such as guilds, learned societies, trading institutions, more decisive? And finally, drawing on the digital design research which is running in parallel with the data

development, how best to structure and present this data so as to enable other researchers to easily explore it and to ask cognate questions of it?

References

Pascal Schillings and Alexander van Wickeren, 'Towards a Material and Spatial History of Knowledge Production: An Introduction', *Historical Social Research* Vol. 40, No. 1 (151), pp. 203-218.

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